

Pyridine Sulphenyl Halides. Part 1

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N-Oxide-2-pyridine sulphenyl bromide has been found to be more stable as compared to known ones. It undergoes nucleophilic reaction with amines yielding sulphenamides. Several compounds possessing high antimicrobial activity were obtained in the course of these synthesis.

In our studies to develop newer blocking agents in peptide synthesis, the use of pyridine sulphenyl halides as α -amino blocking agent was considered. So far pyridine sulphenyl halides have been little studied¹, apart from tetrafluoro-4-pyridine sulphenyl chloride², tetrachloro-4-pyridine sulphenyl chloride³, tetrachloro-2-pyridine sulphenyl chloride⁴ and 5-nitro-2-pyridine sulphenyl chloride⁵. However, these sulphenyl chlorides were so unstable that they existed only in anhydrous conditions and quickly decomposed in open air to their respective disulphides.

Matsueda and Aiba⁶ have reported the synthesis of 3-nitro-2-pyridine sulphenyl chloride and found it sufficiently stable to be preserved for long periods at 0°. The stability of 3-nitro-2-pyridine sulphenyl chloride could be attributed to the neighbouring nitro group *ortho* to sulphenyl chloride which produced strong resonance stabilisation to the molecule owing to the decrease in the basic character of nitrogen atom of the pyridine ring and also due to a specific non-bonding attractive interaction between sulphur and oxygen atom. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to synthesise *N*-oxide-2-pyridine sulphenyl halides, which possess both of these structural features, *viz.* decrease in the basic character of the nitrogen atom of the pyridine ring due to *N*-oxide group and also a non-bonding attractive interaction between the neighbouring oxygen and sulphur atoms. In actual practice, these considerations were found to be sufficiently valid and *N*-oxide-2-pyridine sulphenyl bromide, prepared by the action of bromine on *N*-oxide-2-pyridine disulphide (1) was found to be fairly stable. It could be stored in a desiccator for several days without any decomposition.

N-Oxide-2 pyridine sulphenyl bromide reacted with amines to give sulphenamides (Table 1) in high yields. Compounds 1, 3 and 4 were selected and screened⁷ against different strains of bacterial and fungal infections, of which *N*-oxide-2-pyridine disulphide (1) was found to be most active (Table 2).

2 : X = Br
3-13 : X = Amine

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra were run on a Varian A OD instrument using TMS as the internal reference (chemical shift in τ scale). Uv spectra (MeOH) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 202 spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were recorded on IMS D300 JEOL instrument.

N-Oxide-2-chloropyridine, *N*-oxide-2-pyridine-thiol and *N*-oxide-2-pyridine disulphide (1) were prepared according to the known procedures^{8,9}.

N-Oxide-2-pyridine sulphenyl bromide (2) : Bromine (0.48 g, 0.003 mol) was carefully added to a mechanically stirred solution of *N*-oxide-2-pyridine disulphide (1 ; 0.252 g, 0.001 mol) in dry dichloromethane (5 ml) at 0° and stirred for 1 h. The resultant solid (2) was filtered, washed with CH₂Cl₂ (to remove traces of disulphide) and dried *in vacuo*, yield quantitative, m.p. 125-6° (Found S, 11.08 ; Br, 55.0. C₅H₅Br₂NOS requires : S, 11.17 ; Br, 55.8%). It was found to be stable for long periods in anhydrous conditions but was slowly reconverted into disulphide (1) when exposed to air, in contact with water and also in hydroxylic solvents.

N-Oxide-2-pyridine sulphenamides (3-13) : *N*-Oxide-2-pyridine sulphenyl bromide (2 ; 0.001 mol) was added in small portions to a stirred solution of an amine (0.001 mol) and triethylamine (0.003 mol) in dichloromethane (10 ml) at 10-20°. The compounds (Table 1) were recrystallised from

TABLE 1—N-OXIDE-2-PYRIDINE SULPHENAMIDES

Compd. no.	X	M. p. °C	Solvent of recrystallisation*	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)			
					C	H	N	S
3	piperidino	95	a	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	56.93 (57.14)	6.32 (6.66)	13.10 (13.33)	14.98 (15.23)
4	morpholino	136	a	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	50.73 (50.94)	5.42 (5.66)	13.02 (13.20)	14.90 (15.09)
5	pyrrolidino	134	a	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ OS	55.01 (55.10)	5.87 (6.12)	14.06 (14.28)	16.15 (16.32)
6**	diethylamino	163d	a	C ₁₀ H ₁₇ IN ₂ OS	35.11 (35.29)	4.81 (5.00)	8.02 (8.23)	9.21 (9.41)
7**	N-methylpiperizino	200d	a	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ I ₁ N ₂ OS	28.06 (28.29)	3.98 (4.12)	8.02 (8.25)	5.98 (6.28)
8**	N-phenylpiperazino	138d	a	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ I ₁ N ₂ OS	35.41 (35.72)	3.97 (4.02)	7.10 (7.35)	5.37 (5.60)
9	4'-carbethoxyanilino	179	a	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	57.70 (57.92)	4.63 (4.82)	9.33 (9.65)	10.91 (11.03)
10	4'-nitroanilino	189	b	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	50.01 (50.19)	3.20 (3.42)	15.83 (15.96)	11.95 (12.16)
11	4'-bromoanilino	180	b	C ₁₁ H ₉ BrN ₂ OS	44.14 (44.44)	2.87 (3.03)	9.13 (9.42)	10.51 (10.77)
12	4'-chloroanilino	184	b	C ₁₁ H ₉ ClN ₂ OS	52.11 (52.27)	3.24 (3.56)	10.87 (11.08)	12.51 (12.67)
13	2',4'-dichloroanilino	178	b	C ₁₁ H ₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS	45.76 (45.99)	2.58 (2.78)	9.39 (9.75)	11.01 (11.14)

*aBenzene-petroleum ether, b dichloromethane. **Separated as methiodide salts.

TABLE 2—ANTIMICROBIAL SCREENING

Sl. no.	Infections	MIC* (µg ml ⁻¹)		
		1	3	4
Bacterial				
1.	<i>Streptococcus faecalis</i>	12.5	50.0	50.0
2.	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	12.5	25.0	25.0
3.	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	12.5	25.0	25.0
4.	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	25.0	12.5	12.5
5.	<i>Streptococcus aureus</i>	12.5	12.5	12.5
Fungal				
1.	<i>Candida albicans</i>	12.5	nil**	nil
2.	<i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i>	12.5	nil**	nil
3.	<i>Sporotrichum schenellii</i>	12.5	25.0	25.0
4.	<i>Trichophyton mentagrophks</i>	12.5	25.0	50.0
5.	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	50.0	50.0	50.0

*Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was expressed in terms of micrograms per millilitre at which growth of the test organism was completely inhibited.

**Found to be inactive at test concentration (50 µg ml⁻¹).

appropriate solvent in yields 50-70%. Compound 6 & 8 were isolated in the form of their methiodides.

N-Oxide-2-pyridine sulphenyl piperidine (3) : It showed strong ir bands at 2 950 (methylene), 1 600 (aromatic) and 1 220 cm⁻¹ (N→O). Uv (MeOH) absorption at λ_{max} 242 nm (ε_{max} 20 000) and 320 nm (2 600) confirmed the presence of pyridine ring. Piperidino protons in pmr spectra were observed at τ 8.42 (6H, m) and 7.01 (4H, m) and pyridine protons were found at τ 2.61 (2H), 2.36 (1H) and 1.89 (1H). In its mass spectrum M⁺ was observed at m/e 210 (mol. formula C₁₀H₁₄N₂OS)

and base peak at m/e 84 (M-126) for piperidine nucleus, lent further support for its structure.

N-Oxide-2-pyridine-sulphenyl morpholine (4) : It showed strong ir bands at 2 950, 1 600 and 1 225 cm⁻¹. In its mass spectrum M⁺ was observed at m/e 212 and the base peak at m/e 86 (M-126) for morpholine.

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References

- H. L. YALE in "Pyridine and its Derivatives", ed. E. KLINGSBERG, Interscience, New York, 1964, Part IV, Ch. 15.
- R. E. BANKS, R. N. HASZELCHINE, D. R. KARSA, F. E. RICKETT and I. M. YOUNG, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1969, 1660.
- E. AGER, B. IDDON and H. SUSCHITZKY, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1970, 1530.
- B. IDDON, H. SUSCHITZKY, A. W. THOMPSON and E. AGER, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1974, 2300.
- H. FOX, B. FROHNAU and P. DIFDRICH, U. S. Pat. 2 476 655/1949.
- R. MATSUEDA and K. AIBA, *Chem. Lett. (Jpn.)*, 1978, 951.
- M. L. DHAR, M. M. DHAR, B. N. DHAWAN, B. N. MEHROTRA and C. ROY, *Indian J. Exptl. Biol.*, 1968, 6, 232.
- E. SHAW, J. BENSTEIN, K. LOOSE and W. A. LOTT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4362.
- J. BENSTEIN and K. A. LOOSE, Ger Pat 1224744/1966 (*Chem. Abstr*, 1967, 66, 10853).